

SOME REVIEWS ON THE ACTIVITY OF POLITICAL PARTIES IN MULTIPARTY CONDITIONS

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Abstract

This article discusses the political party and its tasks, issues of increasing the activity of political parties in the multi-party environment. In addition, on the example of the measures implemented by the political parties in Uzbekistan in the regions of Jizzakh region, attention is paid to some aspects of the parties' activities aimed at satisfying the interests of the population.

Keywords: party, multipartyism, election, citizen, activism, human rights, population needs

Introduction

Today, the role of political parties in the political life of society is increasing. Because almost all countries in the world are trying to depart from the path of democratic development and to form state administration on the basis of democratic principles. In this regard, the situation in all countries cannot be said to be the same. Democratic processes require a certain amount of time and factors such as the influence of the historical traditions of the states and the characteristics of the national mentality must be taken into account.

Source analysis

The word "party" comes from the Latin word "part", which means "work", "part". A political party is a part of the population, class, social stratum or strata. A political party is a unique institution of civil society organized and functioning in the form of a public association, which performs important socio-political and representative tasks.

In modern political science, the following aspects that represent the uniqueness of a political party are distinguished:

- any party is the owner and promoter of an ideology that expresses the interests and aspirations of population groups and specific social strata;
- a political party is an organization operating at the level of the republic, region, district and city, which ensures the orderly and continuous unification of people;

- the goal of a political party is to gain the majority of seats in representative bodies of state power in order to be able to advance its programmatic goals that represent the interests of its electorate;

- each political party tries to expand the ranks of its supporters, that is, during the election period, if it works to sway as many voters as possible to its side, and between elections, to attract supporters to the party and their selects and prepares party members and activists from its composition.

The activities of the parties in the socialization of citizens are ultimately related to their goals and the interests of the social groups that empowered them. The ruling parties seek to implement socialization that ensures broad social support for the path they are taking.

The authority to protect the interests of the respective social associations is very important for each party. The party plays an important role in determining the goals and political criteria of the development of the political system and society in general. The extent and effectiveness of this function depends on the position of the party in the political system. In this regard, the ruling parties have the greatest opportunities. They produce and shape the policy that determines the course of action of the entire social system. The internal activity of the party is very important in order to ensure the unity and harmony of the party ranks, to develop values and standards that bring together party members and supporters, to implement leadership and to manage the party's activities.

The important directions of the activity of political parties are as follows:

- identifying, stating and justifying the interests of relevant social groups, their activation and integration;
- creation of political doctrines and programs;
- participation in the struggle for power in the state and in the implementation of state activity programs, state power;
- in general, educating society or a part of it politically, forming social opinion;
- training of personnel for the state apparatus, trade unions, public organizations and promoting them to higher positions;
- organizational activity within the party.

Russian authors V.P.Pugachev and A.I.Solovev's book "Introduction to Political Science" states that there are 3 important signs of democratic parties: the degree of centralization, the degree of participation of parties in politics, and the degree of material support of parties.

When evaluating the activity of political parties, it is necessary to pay special attention to the multiparty issue. First of all, if we explain the concept of "multi-

partyism", in simple words, it is explained by the existence of an atmosphere of competition of more than two parties in the struggle for power in the life of society. That is, we can understand the existence of a system that proposes the participation of more than two parties in political processes, especially elections, alternative projects and reforms in state administration.

"Multipartyism is one of the main constitutional principles of organizing the political life of modern democratic societies. "It is due to multi-partyism that a constant dialogue between political parties and their representatives is ensured, which embodies the main principles of democracy, such as political pluralism, rule of law, equality of opportunities".

Liberalization of all spheres of the political life of the country, in particular, the construction of the state and society, the strengthening of political and economic activity of citizens, the development of the right of people to freely express their will, realize and protect their interests, various interests, opposition - the multiparty system plays an important role in the formation of an effective mechanism that provides a balance between opposing forces and actions.

In this regard, the First President of Uzbekistan, Islam Abdug'anievich Karimov, in his speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 21st anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, put forward the following points about multi-partyism: "To strengthen the multi-party system and develop inter-party competition, the party having its own electorate, having a clear position on the main issues of state and society building, domestic and foreign policy conducted in the country, and gaining prestige between elections are among the most important conditions".

Ijtimoiy-siyosiy va iqtisodiy taraqqiyotning aniq ustuvor yo'nalishlarini belgilab olishda siyosiy partiyalarning rolini keskin kuchaytirish, mamlakatni isloh etish va modernizatsiya qilish bo'yicha strategik vazifalarni hal etishda ularning ishtrokini kuchaytirish izchil amalga oshirilayotgan demokratik yangilanishlarning muhim omili hisoblanadi.

Multipartyism is the result of long-term development of political systems. As a result of reforms to liberalize the activities of political parties in our country, their role in society is increasing. When thinking about "political parties", "state administration", "activities of deputies", their role and importance in the life of people today, in the life of our society, we should consider the interests of the electorate of parties, deputies in our republic, in particular, in regions, districts and localities. zlab's work and measures should be acknowledged. Because, in the minds and thoughts of some people, the opinions formed that party

members or elected deputies are only "owners of the table" should not be proven.

Today, reforms in public administration and other spheres are consistently being carried out in our republic. In this process, increasing the activity of young people, especially women, is one of the urgent issues. Public organizations, especially political parties, have a great role in increasing the socio-political activity of young people, and in the activities of the 5 political parties in our republic, special attention is paid to the inclusion of young people and women. In particular, if we pay attention to the projects and activities implemented by the Democratic Party of "Xalq" Uzbekistan in 2022, within the framework of the "Face to Face with Women" project, N.Allamuratova, deputy of the Council of Zarbdar district, met with women and discussed their problems. It is natural for a country that thinks about the future to pay more attention to the youth. Many conditions have been created for the comprehensive development of the young generation in our country. We can see that educational institutions, sports facilities, libraries, youth centers, in general, the most beautiful buildings of our country were built for our youth. Of course, in addition to teaching our young people knowledge and skills, increasing their political activity and strengthening their legal knowledge is also an important issue.

For this purpose, on the initiative of Ismailov, deputy of the Gallaorol district council of the Democratic Party of "Xalq" Uzbekistan, Jizzakh region, an open roundtable discussion was held within the project "Deputy and Youth", where various problems of young people and the conditions created for them were discussed. The project "Deputy in the neighborhood" was implemented, during which D. Misirov, chairman of the Osmat district council of Bakhmal district, met with families in each neighborhood and heard various problems and suggestions of residents. As we present reforms, projects, and measures, among them, those dedicated to young people and women are important. The project "A healthy woman needs life" was carried out by this party. M.Qoldoshev, deputy of the Zomin district council, member of the Democratic Party of "Xalq" Uzbekistan, supported the women and young people of the population living in the area where he was elected. - Concepts and explanations were given about support and assistance in finding their place in society. In addition, on the initiative of this deputy, qualified medical personnel were attracted to the village family center in this area and women were examined. In 2022, on the basis of the "Support to Youth" project, a job fair was organized in Sh. Rashidov district in order to ensure the employment of young people. They were helped to settle

down. In addition, the event "Women and girls' problems are in the attention of the party" was held in Ravalliq neighborhood of Sh.Rashidov district. Raising the awareness of women, who are the electorate of the party, about the current laws is the most important task facing every party organization. Because in most cases, women's ignorance of their rights has led to their rights being violated. Therefore, the issue of increasing women's awareness of laws should be considered as the main factor in ensuring their rights. Political parties are also working on these issues. Democratic Party of "Xalq" of Uzbekistan considers it important that the people who need social support from their electorate, the state and society, including needy women, should fully know their rights. Its use helps to renew their lives. It is important that a woman who knows her rights can defend herself. It contributes not only to the improvement of one's own life or standard of living, but also to the establishment of public control over certain issues. In addition, the members of the "Ecological Party", which has not yet started its activities, are currently implementing several projects. In particular, one of the most noteworthy projects is the national project "Green Space" based on the decree of the President. Trees and saplings are being planted in the regions under this project. The participation of young people in the implementation of this project is noteworthy.

The activities of the Democratic Party of "Milliy tiklanish" of Uzbekistan are not being ignored. This party is also implementing measures within the "Deputy and Youth" project. In particular, in the Mirzachol district of the Jizzakh region, it is possible to cite as an example the work aimed at increasing the opportunities, conditions and political activity of young people. In addition, within the framework of the "Kizmat-Beminnat" project, the "Youth Wing" of the Jzzax regional council, in order to develop the traditions of "Master-Apprentice" aimed at training young people in free trades and education, "Temir Daftar" and "Temporary unemployed youth included in the "Youth Register" are being trained in additional free trades. And in the first and second quarters of 2022, we can see that over a hundred young people will be involved in the profession on the basis of these training courses.

In addition, on the initiative of the social-democratic party "Adolat" an action was organized in the regions of Jizzakh region under the slogan "We are against corruption". About eight thousand young people and women took part in this action along with party deputies and activists.

Conclusion

In general, social and political activity of the population, especially young people, is very important in the conditions of civil society, which is developing on the basis of multi-party system. That is why the existing political parties in our Republic pay special attention to the youth. Of course, there is still a lot of work to be done in terms of party activity and representation of the interests of the electorate. As President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, "Any political party can survive as a political force only if it is in tune with the times and meets its acute demands." Therefore, in today's era of globalization, in a time when ideological struggles are intensifying, political parties are on the agenda to strengthen their activities based on populist and pragmatic approaches. Ensuring the interests of the electorate on the basis of healthy political competition, focusing on the promotion of promising projects and ideas aimed at developing the country is also in the interests of New Uzbekistan.

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